

THE STATE OF TEACHING THE COURSE “DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION” TODAY

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Abstract. *Digital technologies in education are becoming an integral part of the educational process. The article provides a literary overview of the state of teaching of the course "digital technologies in education". The methods and ways of mastering and applying digital technologies by scientists and teachers are considered.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, information and communication technologies, gamification, augmented and virtual reality.*

It is worth noting that in line with international trends, since 2020, Uzbekistan has introduced the course "Digital Technologies in Education" into the curriculum of universities to train future teachers in the field of information and communication technologies. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to raise the sphere of information and communication technologies to a new level in 2022-2023", the task has been set to annually train more than 6.5 thousand young people in the field of information technology by developing a system of training personnel in the field of digital technologies in the form of distance education [2].

In this regard, scientists and teachers are conducting research and development in the field of mastering digital technologies. Saidova M.Zh. studies the use of information technology in teaching by improving teaching methods [3]. In the scientific work of Yokubova I.R. [6], methodological proposals are presented for improving the professional competence of future specialists using the Prezi Desktop 6.26.0 program, which provide an opportunity for a specific study of language nuances in the classroom. Educational technologies in education have been improved using the developed electronic educational resources. The author has developed an interactive program “Russian Language for Military Lawyers”, an electronic dictionary “Russian-Uzbek-English Dictionary of Legal Terms”, an electronic textbook “Entertaining Russian Language”.

It should be highlighted that Ikramov A.A. [7] suggests using information and communication technologies in his work to improve teaching methods by having students master outdoor games in training, using active teaching methods such as role-playing games that promote deeper understanding of the educational material, and using gamification to increase students' interest in the subject being studied. D.S. Sarimov [8] offers her own method of using information and communication technologies in her scientific work on improving the educational and methodological competence of chemistry teachers in the advanced training system. It is proposed to use virtual and augmented reality in the learning process. The use of virtual reality in laboratory classes allows students to conduct experiments that cannot be carried out in real life and would be life-threatening. And the use of augmented reality will provide an opportunity to create interactive

teaching aids that make the educational material interesting and more visual. In the scientific developments of Akhmedova M.I. [9], an “Uzbek-Latin-Russian-English Electronic Medical Dictionary” was created and implemented on the basis of information technologies, which was compiled on the basis of the results obtained on the formation of professional communicative literacy of medical students in English. After that, the degree of development of professional, grammatical, phonetic qualities of medical students as a result of learning English increased significantly. It is necessary to emphasize the effectiveness of the created special system of teaching English, supplemented by an electronic dictionary, interactive audio tools, multimedia resources. Supplementing the course with relevant video materials, interactive simulations significantly enhances the perception of the material being studied.

Based on information and communication technologies, Choriev I.R. [10] compiled recommendations for the pedagogical design of the process of advanced training. A model of formation and development of readiness for pedagogical design based on information and communication technologies has been created, pedagogical factors of its application have been indicated, modernization of algorithmic procedures of teaching staff training for project activities based on information technologies has been carried out, methods aimed at increasing the efficiency of pedagogical design activities have been created. In the system of higher education in the field of development of experimental knowledge using pedagogical software tools, P. M. Zhalalova [11] put forward proposals for the effective use of information technologies in laboratory classes, the content of step-by-step experimental and virtual experiments on "Atomic Physics" has been optimized. A teaching methodology is presented for the purpose of developing students' creative abilities using the developed set of pedagogical elements for classroom activities; educational and methodological support for laboratory classes has been proposed; based on the assessment of learning outcomes using laboratory developments, the software has been modernized in order to form the professional qualities of future physics specialists.

In the research of Zaripova D.A. [12] the improvement of the system of preparation of students for innovative activity in the field of professional education in the informatization of higher education with the introduction of Smart methods, Smart portfolio, Chalk And Talk was considered; the content of preparation of students was improved with the help of the development of the technology "Network Boomerang" and methods of its use, electronic training resources were created and implemented using the technology "Network Boomerang" based on the programs PHP, Laravel framework, Java Script, designed to develop innovative activity of students in the field of professional education; SMART methods, SMART-portfolio, the technology "Network Boomerang" and the methodology for using its mobile version were created, contributing to the development of innovative activity of students in the field of professional education and introduced into the educational process of a higher educational institution. The use of information technology in education is researched by Kalekeeva T.T. [13] in improving the content of professional training of future computer science teachers, developed a modernization of the process of formation of information literacy and preparedness, proposed a specific methodology for teaching computer science based on the improvement of pedagogical opportunities in educational institutions, and as a result of this - the development of professional competence, scientifically proven proposals are given to optimize the content of training of future computer science teachers.

A similar topic was developed in its own way by Ikramov M.Kh. [14] in the study of improving the methodology for the formation of professional competence of future teachers using the example of teaching the discipline "Technology", using digital educational resources in the

learning processes. Based on digital technologies, Kasimov F.F. [15] researched and developed a methodology for the formation of programming skills in students, proposed ways to use digital technologies to improve the degree of assimilation of educational material and the formation of programming skills in students. The model of the educational process, substantiated by the methodology determining the level and degree of mastery of programming skills, has been optimized. The ways of developing students' programming skills are proposed, a teaching method is built using technologies aimed at developing an algorithm for mastering the programming language with the formation of students' creative abilities in programming.

In the digitalization environment, Mavlyanov N.Sh. [16] proposed an innovative methodology for developing the information competence of preschool educators, revealed the state and problems of using information and communication technologies in improving the level of qualification and ways to solve them, along with this, opportunities for developing the information competence of preschool educators are proposed, a digital platform designed to develop the information competence of preschool educators has been developed and tested in practice. In the scientific research, P. Svyard [3] consistently, in detail and specifically outlined the possibilities of managing digital information content by the information data system of a higher educational institution. In the work of K. White [2], the technology of distance learning is defined.

The development of distance learning organization skills is considered by M. Claro, Salinas and T. Cabellid-Hatt [5] in their scientific work "Learning in a Digital Environment", analyzed testing of pedagogical skills and abilities of Chilean teachers in teaching students methods of solving information and communication problems in a digital environment. All the above-mentioned scientists in their studies demonstrate and emphasize the unique possibilities of modern digital technologies in education, point out the urgent need and relevance of the current level of computer literacy of specialists in all areas and industries of our life. In their studies, M. Schulz and K. Scholz [4] note that with the help of computer technologies today it is possible to collect information on the progress of learning, its trajectory and conduct a rating analysis of learning outcomes, with the development and application of modern digital technologies, and develop an individual learning path. Students and teachers have received unlimited opportunities to develop their educational space and share it. Despite the enormous potential of digital technologies, which is in demand in education, it is not fully used. This is due to the insufficient digital literacy of teachers and leads to the emergence of a digital divide and its overcoming.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be noted that providing training and the ability to use the capabilities of digital technologies is a relevant task of the course "Digital Technologies in Education".

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